

Quality control workflow through the data management lifecycle

3. CMIP5 – highlighting issues.

The Coupled Model Intercomparison Project, Phase 5 (CMIP5) archive provides a testbed for looking at problems of large scale archives. The complexity of the data within the archive is compounded by the complexity of the management structure: in order to facilitate rapid distribution of the climate data, the modelling centres producing the data have set up their own archive nodes. The system is designed to be transparent, so that users can access data without being aware of its location. The transparency breaks down when institutions fail to master the publication process and inject inappropriate information into the system catalogue.

Some issues in the CMIP5 distributed archive

- Version regression: datasets published with a “version” prior to earlier versions;
- Version re-use: A dataset version number is re-used when data is re-published with modified content;
- Version corruption: the data files are changed without re-publishing, so that data is not consistent with catalogue entry;
- Standard access missing: datasets published without support for the default data access mechanism (file download over the http protocol).
- Repeated file entries: the same file appears twice in the catalogue record;
- File name collision: the same file name is used for two different file;
- Temporal overlap: files with overlapping time ranges for a given variable;
- Files do not match the catalogue checksums;
- Checksums and tracking identifiers (used to check provenance of files) not given as required;
- Files published in inappropriate datasets (e.g. data on model levels in a dataset described as holding data on pressure levels).

After resolving all the above issues, users can start looking at the data in the files – and there they may encounter further problems.

1. ExArch: Exascale data analytics

The ExArch project, funded through the G8 Research Council’s Initiative on Multilateral Research Funding, tackles the analysis of extremely large research data collections, with a focus on the CMIP5 archive of climate model projections.

This poster presents work done at STFC to improve the integration of quality control checks into the data archival workflow.

2: Data Archival Workflow

Level 1: Information categories

- File name
- NetCDF Attributes
- Dimensions
- Spatial extent

Level 2: Functional tests

This is the level of general requirements. For example, in the file name group there is a test for compliance of the time range element, in the NetCDF Attributes group there is a test of consistency between global attributes and the file name.

Level 3: Specific tests

The functional tests are expressed in general terms, such as checking global attributes are consistent with specified controlled vocabularies. At the next level of information we have tests of specific attributes against specific vocabularies. E.g. is the value “model_id” attribute in the list specified in the CORDEX RCMMModelNames.txt file?

4: Structuring data quality tests

Tests on data quality cover a wide range of issues. In order to present results clearly, a 4 level hierarchical structure is being developed.

Level 4: Test Elements

Many tests are broken down further. The specification of the time-range string in the file name is generally of the form “yyyymmdd-yyyymmdd”, though often without the “dd” element and sometimes with hours and even minutes specified as well. There may also be constraints on valid start and end months, days or hours. In order to provide a clear error report, and to ensure that the test logic is transparent and robust, the test is broken down into a number of elements, starting from simple generic tests which such as is the hyphen there? Are the two parts of the time range integers and of the same length?